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Research brief: Stakeholder perspective on disaster risk management challenges in five European Pilots

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MYRIAD-EU Pilots: Stakeholder perspective on disaster risk management challenges in five European Pilots

Highlights

- **Pilot Leads have built solid relationships with their stakeholder networks.** This is an ongoing process, which required extensive efforts at the start of the project and evolved with a better understanding of the specific challenges and needs within each Pilot. For example, the lack of information and knowledge about the impacts of multi-hazards in their region, the difficulty of appropriately communicating complex science and its importance to non-scientific audiences, and the varied and competing stakeholder interests.
- **The first round of Pilot workshops was a success.** Consensus was reached on the importance of adopting a multi-risk approach in disaster risk management (DRM). Stakeholders helped prioritise the research questions to be addressed within their regions. Stakeholders confirmed their participation in the next engagement events (including focus groups and interviews).
- Stakeholder engagement in knowledge co-development lead to the identification of **five cross-Pilot DRM challenge themes:**
 - Inadequate governance of multi-hazards and multi-risks
 - Lack of knowledge of multi-hazards and multi-risks
 - Single-hazard and single-sector focus of the existing approach
 - Lack of data and information
 - The complexity of translating science into policy and practice
- **Specific methodological approaches are needed to address multi-faceted and interlinked DRM challenges in each Pilot.** These approaches are co-designed and tested in collaboration with stakeholders over the next project year. Results will be used to inform the multi-risk and multi-sector analysis and develop targeted disaster risk management pathways in each Pilot.

Recommendations

Based on the experience gained in MYRIAD-EU to date, especially through the involvement of stakeholders in research design and knowledge development in the five Pilots, the following recommendations are formulated:

- Engaging stakeholders in the multi-risk assessment and management process at the very onset is fundamental as it improves risk awareness and allows for priority setting
- A multi-hazard and multi-sector approach to DRM is necessary for taking interrelationships and interdependencies into account when developing effective risk reduction options; it also requires and promotes cooperation between institutions and can unlock development and economic potential for regions and communities
- Useful, usable, and used multi-risk assessment and management solutions should be co-designed considering their potential for down-, or up-scaling, where appropriate. This will ensure transferability to other sites and contexts.

Context

In MYRIAD-EU, various methodological approaches for multi-hazard risk assessment and management are co-developed and tested in practice in five European Pilots, i.e. Danube, Scandinavia, North Sea, Veneto, and Canary Islands (Figure 1). A continuous engagement with regional and local stakeholders is ensured for the duration of the entire project and reaches its high points at four events, an Initial and Final Pilot Workshop and two Focus Groups. The Pilots, with the support of the project coordinator team, scientific partners, and Sectoral Representatives, have dedicated the first two years of the project to: i) build the multi-risk profile and understand the governance/regulatory landscape of their region through a comprehensive stocktaking of existing data and information; ii) formulate the DRM challenges for their region after collecting stakeholders' perspectives, experiences, and needs via a series of workshops; and iii) select an appropriate combination of methods for multi-hazard risk assessment and management to (partially) respond to the identified challenges. In a recently submitted paper, we identify and analyse the DRM challenges resulting from the interaction with a vast array of stakeholders (and experts) in workshops organised across the Pilots.

• Figure 1. Overview of MYRIAD-EU Pilots

Want to know more?

- **Full reference:** Robert Šakić Trogrlić et al. Challenges in Assessing and Managing Multi-Hazard Risks: A European Stakeholders Perspective. Submitted to Environmental Sciences and Policy (September 2023)
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